

METHODOLOGY FOR THE SOCIO-ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF THE EU BIO-BASED INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT: The European bioeconomy, crucial for sustainable development, encompasses all sectors that generate value-added products from biological resources, including animals, plants, microorganisms, and derived biomass. The EU's bioeconomy strategy includes an Action Plan aimed at monitoring economic, environmental, and social progress toward a sustainable bioeconomy. Since 2020, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) has been developing the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System, though it has faced challenges due to a lack of data. Consequently, among other reasons, the social perspective has been much less explored compared to other perspectives. This article presents a novel methodology for evaluating bioeconomy sectors using socio-environmental and socio-economic indicators from accessible databases. The methodology enables the analysis of social and environmental impact by integrating data from the Social Progress Index (SPI), facilitating sector comparisons and providing valuable insights to improve socio-environmental indicators in specific value chains.

Keywords: biobased products, socio-economic impact, assessment

1 INTRODUCTION

The bioeconomy encompasses all sectors and systems that produce value-added products from biological resources (animals, plants, micro-organisms and derived biomass, including organic waste), such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy [1]. In this context, the European bioeconomy strategy includes an Action Plan that commits to establishing a coherent monitoring system at EU and international level to track economic, environmental and social progress towards a sustainable bioeconomy [1].

Since its launch in 2020, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) has been developing the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System through the collection of indicators. This development has been hampered by several gaps in indicators and the lack of statistics on emerging and partly bio-based sectors, leading to the generation of new approaches and indicators in the face of said information gaps [2,3].

Moreover, the analysis of sustainability from a social perspective has been much less explored than from other perspectives. An example of this is the lesser attention received by S-LCA compared to the other life cycle methodologies [4]. This underscores the need for methodologies that assess and enable the comparison between sectors from a broader perspective, particularly regarding social indicators.

The present article describes a novel methodology developed with the aim of evaluating the main sectors that constitute the European bioeconomy, although it can be used for any industrial sector and region as far as there's reliable data available. This methodology uses socio-environmental and socio-economic indicators and quantitative data from freely accessible databases. For instance, data from the Social Progress Index (SPI) platform are integrated, enabling the use of either the average global SPI indicator or its sub-indicators, the latter more granular in terms of social aspects.

This methodology was then applied to the Belgian chemical sector as a case study. The contributions of the sector were evaluated from a socio-economic perspective, considering business volume, employment levels, and the "share of bio-based product production".

2 METHODOLOGY DESCRIPTION

2.1 First step - Scope definition

The first step in applying this methodology is to define the scope intended for analysis. If we solely rely on the databases mentioned in this article, the geographical scope of the methodology can only be reduced to the country level. Regarding the sectoral analysis of the bio-based economy, it would be confined to the Textile, Wood and Furniture Production, Paper and Paper Products, Chemicals, Pharmaceuticals, Rubber and Biological Plastics, Biofuels, and Bio-based Electricity sectors. Nonetheless, this methodology can be easily applied to other sectors (not necessarily biobased), specific value chains and regions, provided that there is access to the required data from reliable sources.

2.2 Methodology description and the SPI socio-environmental indicator

Once the country or group of countries to be analyzed and the sectors to be analyzed have been selected, the methodology proceeds with the identification of the main bio-based products consumed in each sector, to then identify the primary raw materials that comprise them. This information can be obtained by consulting the data published by representative entities of the sector or by using Eurostat data [5].

Following the identification of these raw materials, it is essential to gather, for each raw material, the production, import, and export values. In the case of imports, it is also necessary to determine the top three exporting countries and the quantity of the material they export to the country under analysis. Furthermore, the Social Progress Index (SPI) of the countries involved in the analysis must be consulted. This index employs 60 indicators to assess the social performance of 169 countries, with partial evaluations for an additional 27 countries partially. As shown in Figure 1, these indicators are categorized into three groups: basic human needs, foundations of wellbeing and opportunity, further divided into 12 subgroups [6].

Figure 1: Social Progress Index® Framework [6]

In this way, the final SPI value of each country, or any of its encompassing indicators, referred to from now on as Social Progress Rank (SPR), can be associated with the corresponding raw material fraction. That is, the SPR of the country under analysis will be assigned to the fraction of the raw material produced in that country, while the imported fraction will be assigned the SPR of those three exporting countries, considering the weight of each in the exported quantity. As abovementioned, the Social Progress Index is consulted to obtain the SPR values, while the production and import values are obtained from the FAOSTAT database [7].

The objective of all this is to obtain a single value, which will be referred to as the Sector Value (SV), which indicates the socio-environmental impact associated with the selected sector according to 1) the aspects addressed by the SPI indicator itself (as illustrated by Figure 1 above) and 2) the main raw materials of said sector and their dependency on imports from outside EU to cover the market needs. This indicator describes the state of the sector and allows, if desired, the comparison with other sectors for which the SV value has been obtained under the same basis. To obtain the SV, a set of calculation steps is needed. First, it is necessary to multiply the SPR of the country under analysis by the percentage of the corresponding raw material produced within the country ($P\%_m$) (See equation (1)). This step will yield the product value PV_m .

$$PV_m = SPR_c \times P\%_m \quad 1$$

Where:

PV_m is the value of the SPR corresponding to the analysed material m that has been produced exclusively within the selected country (internal production).

SPR_c is the SPR value of the selected country.

$P\%$ is the percentage of production, within the selected country, of the material m being analysed in relation to the total available, which is the sum of the tonnes produced of that material and the tonnes imported into the selected country.

Next, the same procedure is carried out with the export values and the SPR of the three main exporting countries to the selected country. To do this, the exported tonnage from each country was summed, and the corresponding percentage of each country with respect to this sum was multiplied by the SPR of each exporting country (SPR_e). Then, the three values were summed, resulting in a single value (see equation (2)).

$$IV_m = \sum_{x=1}^{x3} \left(\frac{Ex, m}{\sum Ex, m} \times SPR_{e, x} \right) \times I\%_m \quad 2$$

Where:

IV_m is the social index value of the analysed material m which has been consumed in the EU and which is imported.

Ex, m is the quantity of the analysed material m exported to the selected country by one of the three main exporters x .

$SPR_{e, x}$ is the SPR value of the exporting country x .

$I\%_m$ is percentage of importation of the material m , which is being analysed in relation to the total available (Imports + Internal production).

From here, the values obtained earlier are summed,

resulting in a unique consumption value per raw material (See Equation (3)).

$$CV_m = IV_m + PV_m \quad 3$$

Where:

CV_m is the SPR value of the analysed raw material m consumed in the selected country.

Finally, to translate the scores of each raw material to a single score representing the whole sector under analysis, the CV_m of each raw material is multiplied by the corresponding percentage representing the use of that raw material in the sector. The results are then summed, resulting in a value representing the environmental and social impact of each sector (see equation (4)).

$$SV_s = \sum_{m=1}^{m=3} (CV_m \times MS\%_m) \quad 4$$

Where:

SV_s is the value of the SPR of the sector s under analysis.

MS%_m is the share of material m in the total biobased sector studied represented by the three main biobased materials.

These results retain the characteristics of the SPI scoring system, so the lower the score, the worst it is in terms of social and environmental impact for the sector analysed.

2.3 Other socio-economical parameters

With the SV calculated, the methodology might be complemented by incorporating socio-economic data of the bioeconomy from the "Data-Modelling platform of resource economics" of the European Commission [8]. Specifically, the employment, turnover, and bio-based output share values of the sectors and the country under study can be included, since these are relevant parameters commonly reported. Importantly, other social, environmental and technical indicators can be integrated into a study depending on its objectives and available data.

From all the above data and the corresponding calculable value of turnover per employee, each sector of the bioeconomy can be evaluated in detail and compared with the others.

3 METHODOLOGY APPLICATION - A CASE STUDY WITHIN THE BELGIAN CHEMICAL INDUSTRY

To illustrate the use of the methodology, the following case is presented in which the SV related to the Belgian chemical industry is assessed. As this section is intended only to clarify the steps involved in the methodology, the number of products analysed has been limited to one, with surfactants being selected because it is an overall relevant product in the chemical sector, with several applications in cosmetics, cleaning products, food formulations and pharmaceutical products. This analysis

does not consider the size of the surfactants sector in Belgium compared with others, for what a more comprehensive study would be needed to fully dive into the level of importance of certain value chains in this country's context.

When biobased, surfactants can be produced from a wide variety of raw materials, such as plant oils, starch, animal fats, vegetable oils, sugar, starch crops, and natural fibers [9,10]. In this case study, the main biobased raw materials (present in the highest concentration in the products) were molasses, canola oil and sunflower oil. The FAOSTAT database was then used to obtain the percentages of imports and production for each of these raw materials (see Table 1).

Table I: Production and import shares of each of the selected raw materials

Raw material	Imports (%I)	Internal production (%P)
Molasses	68%	32%
Rapeseed or canola oil, crude	56%	44%
Sunflower-seed oil, crude	91%	9%

Additionally, through FAOSTAT, information about the top three countries from which Belgium imports these materials were gathered, as well as their respective shares (see Table 2).

Table II: Export shares of each raw material by the three main raw material exporting countries to Belgium

Raw material	Top 3 non-EU Exporters	Export share
Molasses	Germany	35%
	India	33%
	Netherlands	31%
Rapeseed or canola oil, crude	France	48%
	Netherlands	35%
	Germany	17%
Sunflower-seed oil, crude	Netherlands	60%
	France	29%
	Germany	11%

With the above information defined, the SPR of the countries involved in the analysis were consulted (see Table 3). While this case study uses the global SPR values of each country to showcase the methodology, a

more detailed analysis is possible by diving into other indicators from the SPI platform (see Figure 1), for which quantitative values are also reported.

Table III: SPR values of each country involved in the analysis

Countries	SPR
France	86,07
Netherlands	88,97
Germany	88,72
India	60,19
Belgium	87,22

Once we've reached this stage, we proceed, as previously outlined, to sum the result of the raw material of each country's export ratio by its corresponding SPR, obtaining the value of the SPR_e that corresponds to the fraction of the each imported raw material.

Table IV: Average SPR_e calculation steps for each selected raw material

Raw material	Top 3 non-EU Exporters	Export share	SPR_e	Averaged SPR_e
Molasses	Germany	35%	88,72	79,31
	India	33%	60,19	
	Netherlands	31%	88,97	
Rapeseed or canola oil, crude	France	48%	86,07	87,55
	Netherlands	35%	88,97	
	Germany	17%	88,72	
Sunflower-seed oil, crude	Netherlands	60%	88,97	88,11
	France	29%	86,07	
	Germany	11%	88,72	

This value is then multiplied by the import percentage, while the value for the producing country, in this case Belgium (87,22), is multiplied by the production percentage. These results are summed to generate the CV_m of the material.

Table V: CV_m calculation steps for each selected raw material

Raw material	Averaged SPR_e	I%	P%	IV _m	PV _m	CV _m
Molasses	79,31	68%	32%	53,86	27,99	81,85
Rapeseed or canola oil, crude	87,55	56%	44%	48,70	38,70	87,40
Sunflower-seed oil, crude	88,11	91%	9%	80,53	7,51	88,03

Table VI: SVs calculation steps for the selected sector

Raw material	CV _m	MS%	SV _s
Molasses	81,85	45%	85,09
Rapeseed or canola oil, crude	87,40	29%	
Sunflower-seed oil, crude	88,03	26%	

The analysis indicates that the socio-environmental impact of producing biobased surfactants from the selected materials is relatively low. This is related to the high SPI of the countries that export said raw materials to Belgium – as shown in Table 4, most of these are countries are from the EU, where social indicators tend to be higher. As such, it can be inferred that the expansion of these value chains can promote the development of the biobased chemical sector also from a socio-environmental perspective. When analyzing data from possible applications for surfactants, bio-based pharmaceuticals stand out with the highest employment (13,61k) and turnover (7.020 million €) generation within the biobased economy. Nonetheless, the bio-based output share is rather low (49.2%) [8], with shows the window of opportunity to boost the integration of biobased chemicals into the sector. A more in-depth analysis can also consider the impact of the logistics and conversion steps within each value chain, as well as end of life considerations for the final products and waste streams. By assessing the sector beyond raw material procurement, a more complete understanding of socio-environmental aspects can be achieved. Nonetheless, it is expected that this straightforward procedure combining official EU databases for products and raw materials with a reliable global database of social indicators can serve as a first advance towards the assessment of social impacts in the European bioeconomy.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed methodology can be instrumental to assess the socio-environmental impact of the sectors and/or subsectors comprising the bio-based economy for a country or a group of countries, such as the EU. This evaluation, leveraging reputable sources, yields a single

value, facilitating comparison across various sectors, products, and enabling the impact evaluation along years for example. Furthermore, besides comparison between the selected raw materials, the outputs generated by this methodology may lead to valuable insights and recommendations on how to improve socio-environmental indicators of specific value chains (e.g. by the changing raw material, favoring local sources, or promoting actions to foster social development in regions with low social indicators).

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